

Metabolite classes identified

Total=148

- 56 Amino Acids, Peptides, and Analogues
- 18 Lipids
- 15 Carbohydrates and Carbohydrate Conjugates
- 12 Nucleosides, Nucleotides, and Analogues
- 11 Aromatic Heteromonocyclic Compounds
- 9 Aliphatic Heteromonocyclic Compounds
- 9 Organic Acids and Derivatives
- 6 Aromatic Heteropolycyclic Compounds
- 5 Aromatic Homomonocyclic Compounds
- 4 Aliphatic Acyclic Compounds
- 2 Aliphatic Homomonocyclic Compounds
- 1 Alkaloids and Derivatives

Lipid families identified

Total=491

- 242 Glycerophospholipids
- 159 Glycerolipids
- 46 Sphingolipids
- 28 Steroids and Steroid derivatives
- 16 Fatty Acyls